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Osimertinib and Postoperative Radiotherapy as Combined Regimen in Resected EGFR-Mutated Non –Small-Cell Lung Cancer

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Brankica Milošević Maračić¹, Bojana Poparić-Banđur¹,
Aleksandar Stepanović^{1,2}, Tatjana Arsenijević^{1,2}

¹ Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Pasterova 14 Street,
Belgrade, Serbia

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Medicine, Dr Subotića 8 Street, Belgrade, Serbia

Epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) mutation (m) prevalence ranges from 10–50% in patients with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), with similar rates observed in early-stage and advanced stages. The risk of recurrence following post-operative chemotherapy or other definitive treatment may be increased in patients with EGFRm vs EGFR wild type. Adjuvant osimertinib demonstrated a statistically and clinically significant improvement in overall survival vs placebo in patients with stage IB–IIIA NSCLC. Postoperative radiotherapy (PORT) still plays an important role in stage IIIA NSCLC. However, a question arises whether PORT has a role in a combined regimen with osimertinib in patients diagnosed with IIIA stage, with N2 lymph node involvement. In general, a role for PORT can be found in high-risk patients (≥ 4 N2 disease) and should be discussed when the therapy with osimertinib is planned for the patients in this setting. Nevertheless, additional risk features such as extracapsular extension and/or lymphovascular invasion or R1 resection should be also taken into account for combined treatment. There are no studies to confirm the toxicity profile and treatment outcome of combined PORT and osimertinib. One of the concerns of the previously mentioned treatments is radiation pneumonitis and its grade. In a combined setting with PORT and osimertinib, the toxicity profile potentially could be more prominent and with a higher grade. Further research is needed.

Keywords: Non-small cell lung cancer, radiotherapy, osimertinib

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